

agr! BRIDGES

**“Building bridges between consumers and producers
by supporting short food supply chains through a
systemic, holistic, multi-actor approach-based Toolbox”**

(Grant Agreement 101000788)

Coordination and Support Action

**“Let’s Build our SFSC”
Event Validation Report**

Responsible Partner: Food & Bio Cluster Denmark

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“Let’s Build our SFSC!” Event Validation Report – Denmark

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PU	Public	X
PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including the EC Services)	
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the EC Services)	
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the EC)	

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1. Introduction

The present report summarises the activities of FBCD for the organisation and validation of the “Let’s build our SFSC” event in Denmark organised on 24 May 2023. This event is an online brokerage and networking event, to bring stakeholders of the local agri-food sector to present their products, meet others and negotiate partnerships based on the concept of Short Food Supply Chains. The event was organised using the Brella matchmaking platform that was selected as the most appropriate for the needs of the agorBRIDGES consortium, based on market research and negotiations with the sales departments of various candidate providers, in the frame of task 3.4.

The present report outlines all steps taken for the design, planning and implementation of the regional event, as well as the outcomes and evaluation of the event by the participants and the organising agorBRIDGES partner, to produce suggestions for the improvement of the “Let’s build our SFSC!” tool and measure its impact to the agrifood sector at local level. The remainder of the report is structured as follows:

- **Chapter 1** – Introducing the event report
- **Chapter 2** – Describing the concept selection, design, organisation and implementation of the Online Food Dating event in Denmark.
- **Chapter 3** – Outlining the validation results for the events by participants and the value found in the “Let’s meet!” guidelines by the organising partners when creating and launching their event.
- **Chapter 4** – Concluding remarks for the event and suggestions for improvement of the “Let’s Build our SFSC” tool.

2. “Let’s build our SFSC” event organisation details

2.1 Event programme / agenda

The Online Food Dating event in Denmark took place on 24 May 2023 9:00 – 11:00 CEST. In table 1 you see the detailed programme

Table 1: Event programme

Title of activity	Topic / Short description	Date & Time (local)	Speakers	Location
#1	Welcome and introduction to the platform	9:00 – 9:15	FBCD	Central stage (Fællesrum)
#2	Short Food Supply Chains in Business Region MidtVest	9:15 – 9:45	FBCD	Central stage (Fællesrum)
#3	One-to-one meetings	9.45 – 10.45	N/A	Breakout rooms
#4	agroBRIDGES Toolbox presentation	10:45 – 10:55	FBCD	Central stage (Fællesrum)
#5	Closing	10:55 – 11:00	FBCD	Central stage (Fællesrum)

2.2 Personnel involved in the organisation of the event

Table 2: Estimated effort and expertise needed for the event

Specialisation	Number of employees	Expected role	In-house / External	Estimated effort (person days)
Graphic designers	1	Development of promo material	In-house	2 person days
Session moderator	2	Coordination of the online session	In-house	1.5 person days
Event manager	1	Planning, preparing and	In-house	7 person days

Specialisation	Number of employees	Expected role	In-house / External	Estimated effort (person days)
		recruiting participants		
Event manager	2	Promotion and recruiting participants	External	

2.3 Event material

Vil du gerne sælge direkte til restauranter/caféer/køkkener? Så har du nu mulighed for at møde potentielle kunder online og præsentere dem for dine produkter.

I forbindelse med Madmødet 2023 arrangerer Food & Bio Cluster Danmark et Online Food Dating arrangement, hvor producenter og restauranter/caféer/køkkener kan møde hinanden. Du får i løbet af 2 timer mulighed for at møde op til 4 potentielle kunder og 1 kan have en kort, indledende snak om hvad du kan tilbyde og hvad kunden har behov for. Hvis der opstår 'kemi', kan I evt. aftale et efterfølgende fysisk møde.

Hvis du vil være med, skal vi have din **tilmelding senest 8. maj**. Herefter sender vi invitation til restauranter/caféer/køkkener i hele Region Midtjylland med information om, hvilke producenter de kan møde. Jo flere producenter og jo flere spændende, velsmagende, lokale produkter vi kan præsentere, jo mere attraktivt vil det være for kunderne at deltage.

Meld dig til allerede i dag ved at sende en mail til bs@foodbiocluster.dk.

DET PRAKTISKE

- Arrangementet er online
- Vi bruger matchmaking-plattformen Brella, hvor du skal oprette en profil - du får en udførlig guide, der kan hjælpe dig
- Arrangementet er en del af agroBRIDGES projektet, der understøtter korte forsyningskæder indenfor fødevarer.
- Det er gratis
- Vi skal bruge dit logo, så vi kan præsentere dig i invitationen til restauranter/caféer/køkkener

This event is primarily aimed at producers and restaurants/cafés/kitchens who would like to find new business partners and in the long term enter into supplier agreements with each other in a short supply chain.

In order to increase the likelihood that in particular restaurants/cafés/kitchens would sign up for the event, the strategy was to get min. 10 producers to pre-register so that they could act as 'bait' for buyers in relation to signing up.

Therefore, there are 2 different invitations – 1 for producers (see **Error! Reference source not found.**) and 1 for restaurants/cafés/kitchens, where the pre-registered producers are shown (see Figure 2).

Figure 1: Invitation for producers

Mød lokale fødevarerproducenter på
Online Food Dating

Onsdag d. 24. maj 2023
Kl. 9:00-11:00

Vil du gerne bruge lokale råvarer i dit køkken? Eller bare friske, smagfulde kvalitetsråvarer købt direkte hos producenten? Så har du nu mulighed for at møde Midt- og Vestjyske producenter og høre om, hvad de kan levere.

I forbindelse med Madmødet 2023 arrangerer Food & Bio Cluster Danmark et Online Food Dating arrangement, hvor producenter og restauranter/caféer/køkkener kan møde hinanden.

Du får i løbet af 2 timer mulighed for at møde op til 4 potentielle leverandere og I kan have en kort indledende snak om, hvad du har behov for og hvad producenten kan tilbyde. Hvis der opstår 'kem', kan I evt. aftale et efterfølgende fysisk møde.

Tilmelding
Tilmeld dig senest 19. maj [via dette link](#)

Når du har tilmeldt dig, modtager du et link til Brella-plattformen og en guide til hvordan du opretter en profil.

SPØRGSMÅL
Hvis du har spørgsmål, er du velkommen til at kontakte Britt Sandvad på bs@foodbiocluster.dk eller 2040 9679.

Se producenter du bl.a. kan møde på næste side

DET PRAKTISKE

- Arrangementet er online
- Vi bruger matchmaking-plattformen Brella, hvor du skal oprette en profil - du får en udførlig guide, der kan hjælpe dig.
- Arrangementet er en del af agroBRIDGES projektet, der understøtter korte forsyningskæder indenfor fødevarer.
- Det er gratis

Producenter

	Westjysk Smag: Liker og eddike brygget med kærlighed og smag af den vestjyske natur
	Able Winery: Æblevin - lavet på danske overskudsæbler. Gode til fisk, skaldyr, ost og lyse kødretter
	Søbogaard: Økologisk kvalitet - saft, marmelade, frugtvin, snaps m.m.
	Hønsriet Lystbæk: Høns. Æg. Natur.
	Edgar Madsen / Wapotradning: Håndskåret filet og hel fisk af forsk. pighvar o.a. især fra Nordsøen
	Nørgaards geder: Økologisk malkegedeproduktion i Vestjylland med pt 260 malkegeder plus opdræt
	Bigaarden mellem Hav og Hede: Lokal Mikro Honning med salg af koldpresset, ren, rå honning.
	Lowlands: Snaps brygget på det der vokser i vores omgivende natur
	Hvide Sande Bryghus: Specialøl efter egne opskrifter
	Fjordristeriet: De bedste råvarer og fluid-bed røstning giver en ren kaffesmag. Det er derfor, du vil smage forskel.
	Hestbjerg Økologi: Poppelgrise med 4 velfærdshjerter
	Lille Holmgård Håndbryg: Det gode håndbryggede øl fra eget gårdbryggeri.

Figure 2 Invitation to restaurants/cafés/kitchens

The event was mentioned on [Food & Bio Cluster's website](#) with a short description and registration link (see Figure 3) and in the Food & Bio Cluster's newsletter. Please note that the registration link is no longer available due to the fact that the event has passed.

Food & Bio Cluster Denmark

Medlemmer - Services - **Events** - Nyheder - Netværk - Projekter - Viden

Online Food Dating - Madmødet

Matchmaking

Sted: Online

Pris: Gratis / Free

Fra: 24. maj 2023 kl. 09:00

Til: 24. maj 2023 kl. 11:00

Kontakt

Britt Sandvad
bs@foodbiocluster.dk
20409679

24. maj 2023

I forbindelse med Madmødet 2023 arrangerer Food & Bio Cluster Danmark et Online Food Dating arrangement, hvor producenter og restauranter/caféer/køkkener kan møde hinanden. Du får i løbet af 2 timer mulighed for at møde op til 4 potentielle leverandere/kunder og I kan have en kort, indledende snak om hvad producenten kan tilbyde og hvad køkkenet har behov for. Hvis der opstår 'kem', kan I evt. aftale et efterfølgende fysisk møde.

Når du har tilmeldt dig arrangementet modtager du et link til Brella platformen, hvor du skal oprette en profil, som vi bruger til at matche dig med relevante samarbejdspartnere. Tilmeld dig gerne hurtigt muligt, så du har god tid til at oprette og udfylde profilen inden selve mødet.

Food & Bio Cluster Denmark MADMØDET agr BRIDGES

Figure 3 Event description and registration

The event was organised as part of a large regional event [Madmødet 2023](#) and was therefore displayed in that [programme](#) as well.

2.4 Invitation of attendees and promotional activities implementation

Figure 4: LinkedIn post

(see **Error! Reference source not found.**). The post got 662 impressions.

As mentioned above the strategy for attracting as many participants as possible was to engage the producers first and display them in the invitation to the restaurants.

To support this strategy, we as a first step send the invitation 3 weeks before the event by email to 80 potential producers followed up by a phone call to 30 producers. This resulted in 12 producers signing up for the event and allowing us to use their name and logo in the invitation to the buyers.

Next step was to send the invitation showing the preregistered producers to 25 restaurants that was already engaged in the umbrella-event Madmødet 2023 (2 weeks before the event) followed up by a phone call to 50 restaurants with and outside Madmødet 2023 (1 week before the event). This resulted in 6 registrations from restaurants/cafés/kitchens.

The event was also displayed at the Madmødet 2023 event programme and the Food & Bio Cluster event page and event newsletter.

A LinkedIn post was created which highlighted the producers who had signed up for the event at that time

3. Event implementation and outcomes

3.1 Event implementation

Before the event we encouraged the registered participants to create a profile on the Brella platform in order to be prepared and ready for the actual event and to be able to request meetings with each other. We send several emails containing a step-by-step guide to log in and creating a profile. Despite these efforts, only 13 of 20 participants created a profile beforehand.

The implementation of the event went smoothly except the challenge with no-shows as described below in section 3.2.

The feedback from the participants during the meeting was that they were very enthusiastic about the concept and could see a clear advantage in the time saving aspect and that it gives the opportunity to meet potential business partners that you did not know beforehand.

Therefore, it is also not unlikely that Food & Bio Cluster will make use of the concept at future meetings, but it must be carefully assessed who is the target group and how we can encourage the participants to use the platform to a greater extent prior to the meeting itself.

3.2 Event participation

On the day of the event, there were 20 registered participants – 13 producers and 7 restaurants/cafes/kitchens. Of these, 15 participants had created a profile on the Brella platform, as can be seen in Figure 5. That number includes 2 people from Food & Bio Cluster Denmark - so in reality 13 external profiles were created. Before the start time, we received cancellations from 2 producers. A further 6 restaurants and 2 producers never showed up to the event. That is that there were 9 producers and 1 café at the event. Since the purpose of the event was to match producers with buyers of the locally produced products, it was not an appropriate composition. The one buyer who was present was fully booked with 4 meetings. In addition, individual producers had meetings with each other or with a representative from Food & Bio Cluster Denmark. A total of 8 meetings were thus held during the event, as shown in Figure 5.

From the registrations, we can see that 7 registered companies never created a profile, despite detailed instructions and offers of support from the organiser. Unfortunately, we have no knowledge of what has prevented them from creating a profile, despite the fact that they have registered for the event.

Of the 13 who actually had a profile created, 3 did not appear. We got hold of 1 of them by telephone and here the explanation was that an urgent task had come across. We didn't catch the others, so we don't know why they end up not showing up despite having spent time creating a profile.

100% of the 8 meetings held were requested during the event. None of the participants had requested meetings in advance.

Table 3: Event participation

Audience type	No. of participants
Producers	9
Restaurants/cafés/kitchens	1
Total	10

4. Event Validation

4.1.1 Validation of event by participants

A questionnaire was sent to participants by email directly after the event. 6 of the participants answered the questionnaire.

Question	Answer					
	Yes	No	Not sure			
Were you familiar with the concept of Short Food Supply Chains before this event?	2	4	0			
	Very helpful	Helpful	Neutral	Not very helpful	Not helpful at all	I prefer not to answer
Did you find this event helpful to meet professionals and businesses you can collaborate with?	0	4	1	1	0	0
	Very useful	Useful	Neutral	Not very useful	Not useful at all	I prefer not to answer
Do you think that this event helped you see Short Food Supply Chains as a promising business alternative?	1	4	0	1	0	0

Question	Answer					
	Very useful	Useful	Neutral	Not very useful	Not useful at all	I prefer not to answer
Did you find the matching and booking of one-to-one meetings with other people useful to identify and negotiate collaborations?	1	2	2	0	1	0
Was the event useful in supporting you to find interesting opportunities to collaborate with other businesses for the development of Short Food Supply Chains?	1	3	1	0	1	0
Would you like another similar event to be organised in your region? How often?	Monthly or more often	3-4 times a year	Twice a year	Once a year	Never	I prefer not to answer
	1	2	2	1	0	0

One of the participants stated this in the evaluation questionnaire:

I believe that the outcome will be bigger if there are as many buyers as providers and I would recommend finding buyers before providers. Ideally, there are new buyers invited the 3-4 times a year to meet and the same with providers. Can see many possibilities.

4.1.2 Validation of the “Let’s build our SFSC” event by the organising partner

Question #1: Did you find the event relevant to your local agri-food ecosystem and organization?

In theory this type of event should be relevant to producers and restaurants in the agri-food sector in order to meet each other and develop a cooperation. Both parties claim that it is difficult to find time, so this time saving concept should be exactly what they need. But since we experienced difficulties in recruiting participants despite a quite intensive effort (direct phone calls), one can question if it is the right concept.

Question #2: Would you organise the same event again in your region? If yes, would you make any adjustments? If not, please explain your thinking.

Since the producers that actually participated in the event were very positive and enthusiastic about the concept, it might be worth trying again. As suggested by one of the participants, we would commit the buyers first since they turned out to be the most difficult.

4.1.3 Limitations and barriers of the organising partner

As mentioned above, it was extremely difficult to recruit participants for the event and we ended up doing a telephone campaign to ensure a sufficient number - and still ended up with too few and a skewed distribution anyway. So, the biggest challenge is that in this way it becomes a very resource-demanding and costly activity that can hardly be defended from a cost-benefit point of view.

5. Conclusions

Our impression is that the Brella platform is user-friendly and constitutes a good and useful platform for matchmaking. The participants we had at the meeting were very enthusiastic about the concept. So, the challenge clearly lies in getting companies to sign up - and get them to create a profile. It requires manual effort and a lot of guidance.